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AI Pioneers: Developing a Community of Practice for Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Vocational Education and Training

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Abstract

This paper examines the implications of VET and for VET of digital and sustainable socio-economic development. It examines the dual challenge of AI as a tool for teaching and training in VET but also as a subject for learning in VET. It quotes UNESCO (2022) in saying AI has the potential to accelerate the process of achieving the global education goals through reducing barriers to accessing learning, automating management processes, and optimising methods to improve learning outcomes. It looks at current advances in AI including their potential impact on work organisation, work tasks and business processes and the potential and challenge for education and the research and social challenges this poses for research in Vocational education and Training. The research suggests everyone needs to be able to recognize AI and its influence on people and systems, and be proactive as a user and citizen. VET students should have the opportunity to use AI and big data to solve problems, for instance maintaining systems in the mechatronic occupations. Thirdly, VET dual students (higher level apprentices) should become skilled in computer science for developing AI systems. The paper goes on to examine the new skills and competencies needed by VET teachers and trainers and professional development requirements. It concludes with the aims of the Erasmus Plus AI Pioneers project to develop a community of practice around AI in VET.

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence (AI), vocational education and training, VET students, VET teachers

1 AI, Education and VET

This paper examines the implications of VET and for VET of digital and sustainable socio-economic development. It examines the dual challenge of AI as a tool for teaching and training in VET but also as a subject for learning in VET. The paper is based on the work of a European consortium of VET researchers and developers on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and VET. Having initially developed a strategic partnership with funding from the EU Erasmus Plus programme,

an expanded partnership has been successful in gaining EU support for a large-scale project, AI Pioneers, which started in January 2023.

1.1 The potential of AI for education

Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be defined as a computer system that has been designed to interact with the world in ways we think of as human and intelligent. Ample data, cheap computing and AI algorithms mean technology that can learn very quickly. The transformative power of AI cuts across all economic and social sectors, including education. UNESCO (2022) says AI has the potential to accelerate the process of achieving the global education goals through reducing barriers to accessing learning, automating management processes, and optimising methods to improve learning outcomes.

A European Joint Research Council policy foresight report (Tuomi, 2018) suggests that "in the next few years AI will change learning, teaching, and education. The speed of technological change will be very fast, and it will create high pressure to transform educational practices, institutions, and policies." They say it is therefore important to understand the potential impact of AI on learning, teaching, and education, as well as on policy development.

1.2 Large language models

The current advances in AI, particularly Large Language Models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT or Robotic, are based on processing large volumes of data from the internet. Machine learning enables a machine or system to produce meaningful results without being specifically told beforehand what to do. As a result, tasks that were previously performed by human activity are now potentially dependent on AI aided automated systems. It has been suggested that just as automation has threatened lower skilled work, the new AI system may automate skilled work (Lowrey, 2023). While such AI systems have much potential in education, for instance reducing the amount of administrative work teachers have to undertake, and developing curriculum and learning materials, ChatGPT has been seen by some as a challenge particularly for traditional forms of assessment (Khalil, 2023).

2 The research challenge

The rapid development and implementation of AI poses a series of research and social challenges for Vocational Education and Training and Adult Education. These include:

What changes are needed to curricula to deal with the increasing use of AI in all areas of society?

How will AI change working practices and the knowledge and skills required in different occupations?

What is the relation between human intelligence and skill and Artificial Intelligence? How can humans work together with machines?

How can we ensure that the development of AI is not just the preserve of very large multinational companies?

What are the ecological impacts of AI?

What are the competencies and skills required for VET and Adult Education teachers and trainers?

How can we organise sufficient opportunities for VET teachers and trainers?

How can we use AI effectively for teaching and training and for extending opportunities and access to education and train

What will be the impact of Large Language Models on assessment and evaluation?

How can we ensure that we provide equal opportunities for research and development of AI?

How do we address the ethical issues raised by AI not just in society and work but also in education?

What policies are required to deal with the challenges of AI?

A major challenge for research and development is the very spread of developments in this area. ChatGPT, which was only released in November already has more than one million signed up users. Perhaps one immediate challenge is how we can use AI in our research and development activities.

3 Changing work and business processes

The introduction of AI based systems is leading to changing work and business processes spanning many industries, with changing requirements for professional skills of skilled labour (Verma, 2023). This is often accompanied by the fear that human labour will be replaced on a large scale and professions and occupations can lose meaning and importance for structuring vocational education and training. In the scientific discourse, the view prevails that professional activities will change significantly, which means that some jobs will be lost, initially routine activities, but also new professions or new ranges of activities in existing occupations will emerge. There is not necessarily a complete substitution taking place, but the use of AI-based systems lead to the redesign of work. The increase in efficiency and productivity are driving factors for companies in industry, supply, manufacturing and software design to follow up such developments. From the employee's point of view, there are positive sides to the introduction of AI, for instance relief from physically demanding work or tiring routine tasks, or cognitive support for undertaking complex tasks. However, the social and ethical impact of AI is under debate: What is an AI system allowed to do and what is it not allowed to do? Who should participate in AI-based projects and development? Who is responsible for the consequences of AI-based applications? (Lufkin, 2017).

It has been suggested that workers should be equipped with at least basic knowledge about AI, both to help ensure their own employability but also their ability to shape the future of work like we do want to have. Vocational education and training can be a key element in dealing with AI technologies. Given these important and rapid shifts, it is time to consider what VET students (apprentices, trainees, technicians) need to know about AI technology. Firstly, our research suggests everyone needs to be able to recognize AI and its influence on people and systems, and be proactive as a user and citizen. Second, VET students should have the opportunity to use AI and big data to solve problems, for instance maintaining systems in the mechatronic occupations. And thirdly, VET dual students (higher level apprentices) should become skilled in computer science for developing AI systems.

Recognizing AI is an initiative by leading computer scientists that have identified five big ideas that VET students should know about AI (AI4K12, 2020):

- Computers perceive the world using sensors. Examples include speech recognition and computer vision; emerging issues include the nature of intelligence and the limitations of human and computer perception.
- Agents maintain representations of the world and use them for reasoning. Examples include types of algorithms, the work they do and their limitations.
- Computers can learn from data. Examples include types of machine learning - yet there are concerns about issues such as bias in training data.
- Intelligent agents require many types of knowledge to interact naturally with humans. Examples include interacting with digital assistants, chatbots and robots. Emerging issues involve the nature of consciousness and limitations of AI interaction.
- AI applications can impact society in both positive and negative ways. Emerging issues include the use, fairness and transparency of algorithms and likely social impacts.

4 Vocational education and training and the European Digital Education Action Plan

The education sector finds itself in a double tension. On the one hand, it is responsible for preparing young people for the changing world of work. On the other hand, educational institutions and teachers and trainers are under pressure to adapt to adopt digital technologies. This is particularly the case in vocational training. Teachers and trainers in VET are responsible for training the workforce of the future, which will include the development and use of AI systems and for whom knowledge is linked to a new understanding of the work processes. For example collaborative robotics can allow workers to undertake more complex tasks than before. These pressures are leading to the development of new projects in the vocational schools including the extension of the curriculum around AI, but the resulting freeing up of time from the existing school curricula.

The TacCLE AI project undertook a series of case studies in vocational schools and the workplace in different European countries. This resulted in the following policy recommendations: (Attwell, Deitmer et.al., 2021):

1. Update of VET curricula by including AI topics.

Artificial intelligence has the potential to change many areas of life. It is therefore important that (young) people are fully informed about the potential benefits and limitations of AI for digital learning. In addition, apprentices need knowledge of how to use the latest AI-based applications in their occupational areas. The discussion of ethical and legal issues must be given special priority including data privacy.

2. Incorporate teaching competences for AI for VET teachers and trainers. If we incorporate AI in VET curricula it is self-evident that we need to include it in training programmes for VET teachers and trainers as well. The extent to which the topic of AI should find its way in depends on the respective area of learning / vocational field. Nevertheless, it is important that VET teachers and trainers have a basic knowledge of AI in order to assess developments in the labour market and new trends in educational technologies. Knowledge about AI should also be sought beyond professional activities, as AI also affects the everyday lives of VET teachers and trainers.

3. Encourage and support the development, searchability and sharing of Open Educational Resources for AI in VET. Due to the speed of the digital transformation, it is useful to bundle competences and share knowledge under VET teachers and trainers. In the field of education, the sharing of Open Educational Resources can support new learning programmes on AI and digital learning.

4. Encourage and support the development of online programmes of Continuing Professional Development for AI in VET. Digital transformation opens up the opportunity to make learning more flexible. This is also true for the Continuing Professional Development of teachers and trainers. Applications for digital interaction such as forums, Massive Online Courses (Moocs), chat groups or shared comments can promote exchange between VET stakeholders.

5. Support collaboration between industries, VET schools and training centres. This is in order to develop new training projects in the use of AI in different occupations in order to update their own knowledge and competences in the use of AI in different occupations. In addition to sharing knowledge between educational institutions, it is crucial that all stakeholders involved in VET work more closely together. Educational institutions need to know from companies how the latest technologies are already affecting their business in order to know what to teach.

At a European level the Digital Education Action Plan (European Commission, 2021) has adopted two strategic priorities. The first is to support the development of a high-performing digital education ecosystem and the second to address the need to enhance digital competences for the digital transformation. It is stated that a high performing digital education ecosystem

will increasingly include the use of AI at all levels including for teaching and learning. The action plan says that “digital technology, when deployed skilfully and effectively by educators, can fully support the agenda of high quality and inclusive education and training for all learners”.

The Tackle AI and Vocational Education and Training project has identified additional competences for AI based on the European Commission DigCompEdu framework of competencies for educational practitioners (Attwell, Deitmer et.al., 2020).

5 VET teachers and trainers

The initial Erasmus+ project, AI and VET, was mainly directed towards researching the use of AI by VET teachers and trainers and at developing their confidence and competence in AI. This included research on the changing labour markets and the implications of AI for VET curricula as well as the practices of teachers and trainers. A survey and interviews (Roppertz, 2020) with teachers and trainers found little resistance to the use of AI in their teaching practice, but there is still massive demand for the professional development opportunities and for examples of how they could teach AI.

The use of AI in VET differs from AI in general education in that it has a dual focus: school learning and workplace learning. AI can be used in VET for teaching and learning, for example using chatbots (like GPT3 or others) for example to extend formative e-assessment and feedback as well as personalised learning. But AI is also a subject for VET, as it is increasingly adopted in different occupational competences and practices.

However, it is one thing to identify the competencies needed, it is another to provide sufficient opportunities for professional development to ensure ALL VET teachers and trainers are supported in updating their competences.

In this regard we recognise that traditional training courses for Professional Development may not be sufficient to meet the needs. Therefore, we would urge an approach supporting more flexible and innovative opportunities for Professional Development including in particular blended and online learning programmes.

These considerations have led us to develop the following recommendations.

- Incorporate competences for AI into all initial training programmes for VET teachers and trainers
- Encourage and support the development, searchability and sharing of Open Educational Resources for AI in VET
- Encourage and support the development of online programmes of Continuing Professional Development for AI in VET
- Support collaboration between industries; craft trade; VET schools and training centres to develop new projects and curricula and in the use of AI in different occupations.

To provide professional development opportunities for teachers and trainers, the AI and VET project developed a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). The MOOC was flexible, initially running online for three months, and now freely open to participants. In the initial three months, nearly 500 people signed up, with almost equal numbers for the English and German language versions.

A key issue in researching and supporting the use of AI in education and training is the issue of ethics. The AI and VET project produced a research report (Attwell, Bekiadis et al, 2021), drawing attention to issues like bias, the lack of transparency in algorithms and unequal access to digital content and resources. The European Commission has recently launched a set of ethical guidelines for educators on the use of AI and data in education (European Commission, 2022). Work on this area will continue in the new AI Pioneers project.

6 Exemplar case study of an AI project in VET

The topic of the project was Deep Reinforcement Learning –“= artificial intelligence” and implementation of an agent in the game “Sonic the Hedgehog” (Attwell, Deitmer et al., 2021). Sonic is a computer game from the Japanese publisher, Sega. The goals for the project were:

- (1) To acquire an understanding of artificial intelligence and neural networks
- (2) To gain advanced knowledge of the Python programming language
- (3) The AI should master different levels independently.

Trainees of the vocational school course for “information technology assistants” (German: “Informationstechnische(r) Assistent(in)”) took part in the second year of training within the framework of the learning field “Planning, implementing and evaluating projects” (practice). The total time required was 160 hours per school year.

What did trainees learn in the project? The trainees were able to acquire both technical and social skills in the course of this project. On the one hand, they learned project-oriented work in a group; they set themselves goals and divided and organised their work independently. On the other hand, they independently dealt with a programming language (Python) that was new to them and learned its basics to the extent that they were able to understand, modify, and create programs. In addition, the trainees have dealt with the basics of neural networks and different terms of machine learning, so that they were able to present the basics to their fellow students and explain the terms.

Reflection and recommendations for other teachers: since the students have to deal with the topic of artificial intelligence in their future work, it makes sense to deal with it in the vocational school. In the project documentation, the students report that it was surprisingly easy to acquire basic knowledge about AI. However, they emphasise that the deeper immersion in the subject matter was an obstacle, as more complex mathematical knowledge would have been necessary. This sometimes led to lower motivation and productivity. Overall, however, the students report that the choice of project was a good decision and that they have gained an advanced understanding of AI and its practical implementation.

When asked about what needs to happen on the part of the school and the teachers so that such projects can be practised regularly, the teacher reported that, on the one hand, appropriate further training for the teachers is necessary. Besides the transfer of knowledge about AI, the joint development of teaching concepts should be more important. In addition, existing teaching materials should be jointly reviewed and classified. The teacher recommends that the students have a say in choosing the appropriate topic. Students need motivation and perseverance to work in project groups, so it is an advantage if the project tasks are linked to the students’ interests. In addition, clear evaluation criteria should be established and communicated transparently.

7 Conclusion: AI pioneers

The questions and issues emerging from the previous research and activities in the AI and VET project are being taken forward in the new AI Pioneers large scale Erasmus+ project launched in January 2023 and running to December 2025. The project directly addresses the issues of capacity, both systemic and institutional, through working with teachers and trainers, educational planners, stakeholders, and policy makers in Adult Education and Vocational Education and Training, to identify, develop and pilot use cases of artificial intelligence in education and training including considering their impact on data, privacy, ethics and EU values. The project will develop a supplement to the DigCompEdu Framework for the skills and competences related to the use of AI in education. It will also produce recommendations, toolkits and implementation guidelines on the role and use of artificial intelligence. Central to the project is the development of a network of AI pioneers as a Community of Practice.

Online communities of practice (CoPs) can be a valuable resource for AI pioneers in education who are interested in exploring the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning in the classroom. Such CoPs can provide a platform for educators to collaborate and share best practices, resources, and experiences related to the use of AI in education. By participating in online CoPs, AI pioneers can gain access to a wider range of perspectives and expertise and stay up to date on the latest trends and best practices in the field of AI. They can also collaborate on projects and initiatives, and receive feedback and support from other members of the community. In addition, participation in online CoPs can help participants to strengthen their commitment to their profession by fostering a sense of community and shared purpose. By connecting with other like-minded individuals who are passionate about AI, AI pioneers can feel more inspired and motivated to continue their own professional growth and development.

The term Pioneers is taken from DigCompEdu (Redecker, 2017) and is defined as follows: “Pioneers question the adequacy of contemporary digital and pedagogical practices, of which they themselves are Leaders. They are concerned about the constraints or drawbacks of these practices and driven by the impulse to innovate education even further. Pioneers experiment with highly innovative and complex digital technologies and/ or develop novel pedagogical approaches. Pioneers are a unique and rare species. They lead innovation and are a role model for younger teachers.”

That such innovation is necessary has been amply illustrated by the challenges and debate not just in the education community but in popular media by the release of ChatGPT and the forthcoming Bard application.

Ethics Statement

There are no ethical implications to this research

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Biographical notes

Graham Attwell is the founder and Director of Pontydysgu. He is an experienced researcher and developer and is an expert in digitalisation and Labour Market Information. He is a specialist in the use of technology for teaching and learning and for knowledge development. He is experienced in modularisation, the recognition of prior learning and in work based and vocational education. He is experienced in the development of flexible programmes and formats of learning including micro-modules or learning bites and MOOCs. He has recently developed a MOOC for AI for VET, through the Tacple AI Erasmus + project.

George Bekiaridis is Chief Executive of Active Citizens Partnership. Has long experience of working with European funded and transnational projects. He is specialised in research and development into digital pedagogies and technology enhanced learning, the recognition of informal learning, the training of teachers and trainers and development of open-source software for education and Open Educational Resources. George Bekiaridis participated as researcher in Tacple AI and AI@School projects.

Ludger Deitmer's research interests focus on work-based learning in technical occupations, design of in-company training, evaluation the quality of apprenticeship, the governance of regional VET systems, and enhancing innovation by training. He participated in the Tacple AI and in the AI and school Erasmus+ projects. For Tacple AI he analysed project cases studies in 8 VET colleges as well as undertaking an AI literature review and the development of policy recommendations.